

SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF WORDS AND PHRASES EXPRESSING THE CONCEPT OF "HAPPINESS" AND "UNHAPPINESS" IN ENGLISH.

Aliyeva Nargiza Tulkinovna

Teacher of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8069478>

Abstract: This article deals with the concept of "Happiness" and "Unhappiness" in English the national-cultural characteristics of phraseological expressions and the translation of these phraseological units into Uzbek have been shown.

Key words: linguistic and cultural science, concept, phraseological unit, paremiology.

In the English and Uzbek languages, the lexemes "happiness" and "bakht" are one of the concepts that express human feelings. Although the lexeme of happiness as a separate concept means specific feelings of trust, it is also connected with feelings of love and friendship. In English and Uzbek languages, in many cases, achieving love is connected to the concept of happiness. After all, achieving love also represents the concept of achieving the content of a happy life. In fiction, the duality of happiness and unhappiness between people is connected with the kindness of the tole. This duality can be not only the object of influence of higher forces, but also the object of good deeds that show their will and ability to influence a person. Happiness is a specific feeling, that is, it represents the concept of achieving the content of a happy life, and there are also characteristics of not achieving such happiness, which gives rise to the concept of the dyad of unhappiness. Happiness coexists with unhappiness. Happiness is achieved gradually, and unhappiness comes with flapping wings. From misfortune comes the meaning of bad luck. Lexical annotations and competent definitional analysis show that the meaning of happiness in English is "happiness", and the meaning of "bad luck" is related to the duality of different fields. Concepts such as happiness and poverty in human life appear through them. There are different forms of lexemes that reflect this relationship. They are represented by the lexeme "Unhappiness" to one core, that is, the concept of "happiness". Failure is an accident. It shows unexpected disappointments.

Therefore, the concepts of happiness and unhappiness can be considered as independent concepts. This is known to us that every person strives to live a happy life and avoid unhappiness. As a person's knowledge and life experience increases, his ideas about happiness change and take shape. If we look carefully at the history of mankind, it can be observed that people's thoughts, ideas and imaginations about this notion or concept are connected with consistency. The thinkers of the past have proven in their works that the concept of "happiness" is manifested in different situations and emphasized that it is one of the highest feelings of a person in social life. In this regard, a lot of stories and narrations, wisdom and proverbs - paremias have been created in the national language. The concept of "happiness" is understood differently by everyone. For example, one of the wise men wrote about happiness, bliss and life in a letter to his son: "Dear son, listen carefully to my words. Don't join the ranks of those who struggle because they are not lucky, if you work hard, you will get what you want. Maybe some of your work will not turn out as successful as you

wish, but don't worry about it and despair. Don't lose your enthusiasm and courage. From what seems to be difficult and difficult, in reality, many important and good results can be produced. Don't get too carried away by trivial things and material decorations. Strive to be a perfect possessor of grace. Take a lesson from the lives of great people in history. Be kind, compassionate, and gracious. All these are the foundations of happiness" [5]. Socrates says: "A man who is satisfied with little things is a statesman, because such contentment shows his spiritual wealth." There is nothing in the world that a person can't overcome, so don't be afraid, use your energy and enthusiasm and move forward. Do not think that happiness and bliss will fall from the sky or appear out of nowhere. If you think like this, you will be considered one of the most ignorant people in the world" [2]. Happiness does not consist only of material world, career or fleeting feelings. Every blessing of God is happiness. Muhammad Mustafa (peace be upon him), the master of two worlds, said: "Whoever wakes up in the morning with his house safe, his body healthy, and his daily food, it is as if the whole world is gathered for him."

When analyzing words and phrases expressing the concepts of happiness and unhappiness in English, first of all, we need to have a comprehensive understanding of foreign language words and their scope of use. Because, as in Uzbek, in English, each word has its own meaning and places of use.

Words and phrases representing the segment of happiness are found in abundance in all languages. Including, in the English language that we are now considering, there are several objects that express the concept of happiness.

It should be noted that a certain idea of happiness is one of the main points, which determines the way to perceive oneself as an objective reality. Humanity builds its world on the basis of these ideas of happiness. People cannot live without making any judgments about the concepts of happiness.

According to dictionaries, the word happiness is formed as an adjective "happy" and a noun with the suffix "bakht". In the etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language, "happiness" is given as a Persian derivative. The analysis of etymological dictionaries shows that the concept of "happiness" has semantic and linguistic aspects. Comparative descriptions of the concept of "Happiness / Unhappiness" form a number of synonyms in English: There are also synonyms in the Uzbek language: happiness, luck, happiness, joy, luck, masud, pleasure, pleasure, satisfaction. The analysis shows that synonymous semantic correlative pairs are observed within the concept of "Happiness / Happiness":

- glad — satisfaction (Rejoice)
- fortunate — ikbol, good luck
- contentment pleasure, satisfaction (satisfaction).

In both languages, the concept of "happiness" means luck and satisfaction. There are some examples in English: wealth (happiness) is often found but hard to keep (happiness is easy to find, hard to keep), luck is good to him, he knows how to use it well (laughter is happiness, who knows how to use it well), good luck (rely on your luck); lucky at cards, unlucky in love (lucky at cards, unlucky in love), better born lucky than wise (better born lucky than wise).

In Uzbek:

- lucky thing has its time
- if luck comes, mouse win an elephant

Happiness comes by making effort, honest work

- a good habit will bring you happiness (Honest work will lead to happiness)

- labor - it is the light of happiness- (labor - it is the light of happiness).

As a result of the comparative analysis of lexical phraseological units, the concept of "happiness" in English and Uzbek languages was determined as a similar and unique singularity. Similar associations between the concepts of "happiness" and "unhappiness" are shown in the following categories: - Happiness - children: he does not know what love is because he does not have children (does not have children, does not know his value). The happiness of the child is the throne of the mother, the perfection of the child is the beauty of the father (the happiness of the child is the happiness of the parents). - Happiness is work: early to bed and early to rise makes a person healthy, rich and wise. Work brings happiness. Happiness is courage: luck favors the brave, (luck is always good for the brave), Fortune gives a handle to the chaser, not the one who runs away (fortune catches the one who runs after, not the one who runs). Moreover, according to the national outlook, everyone in both nations builds his own happiness: he is the architect of his own happiness, and each person is the architect of his own wealth. Association in Uzbek language:

-Happiness — Knowledge: Knowledge brings happiness

- Happiness — Time: it took time — happiness is gone.

- Happiness — Union: happiness — in the Union.

Happiness comes in a joyful house.

- Happiness — Friendship: pledge of happiness — friendship.

- Happiness — destiny: happiness in the chest and key in the sky.

- Happiness — Success: happy hunter meets lame deer.

- Happiness — loyalty: faithful man is happy

In Britain, luck is associated with: - Happiness - Health: good health is better than wealth (it is better to be healthy than rich). - Happiness is a career: create a career for yourself. - Happiness - glory: conquering the world (achieving good success, conquering the world for universal recognition). - Happiness is a goal: to bring one's mind to pass, to fulfill, to have or to possess (seek its goal). As an analysis of the linguistic material, in both languages, "Happiness" is a positive evaluation in terms of positive emotions. However, in the Uzbek language, happiness may not always come in a positive sense. He sees a negative meaning in this. For example, saying "Someone's happiness, someone's eyes went out" translated as (someone's happiness, someone's misfortune) means that not everyone can be happy with someone's happiness. The concept of "happiness" has figurative units in Uzbek language: - Bakht - Poultry: The bird of happiness landed on his head (the bird of happiness on his head). - Happiness is the theme: Try Bakhtin (Experience happiness), Bakhtin Berminak (Give happiness). - Happiness is a living organism: Happy smiling (Smiling happiness). A lucky person is lucky.

In this regard, several more examples can be given: - May the child be happy / may his happiness be revealed (may the girl be happy) - fear the khan's throne, the girl - fear her happiness (the king is afraid of losing his throne and the girl due to his happiness is afraid) - do not wish the girl a golden throne, but happiness like a finger (do not wish the girl a golden throne, but wish her good happiness) - the happiness of the girl is the state of the husband (the happiness of the woman is the wealth of the husband) - there is a time for everything, the happiness of every girl there is (everything has a certain time, because every girl has her own

happiness). The state of happiness in linguistics is "happy", " beatitude ", " blessedness ", " bliss ", " blissfulness ", " felicity ", " gladness ", " joy ", " warm fuzzies ", " elatedness ", " elation ", " exhilaration ", " exultation ", " high ", " intoxication ecstasy ", " euphoria ", " glory ", " heaven ", " nirvana ", " paradise " , " rapture " , " rapturousness ", " ravishment ", " seventh.heaven ", " transport delectation ", " delight ", " enjoyment ", " pleasure cheer ", " cheerfulness ", " comfort ", " exuberance ", " gaiety (also gayety)", " gladsomeness ", " glee ", " gleefulness ", " jocundity ", " jollity ", " joyfulness ", " joyousness ", " jubilation ", " jubilation ", " lightheartedness ", " merriness ", " mirth content ", " contentedness ", " gratification ", " satisfaction " , " triumph " ; " suitability ", " suitability ", " agreeableness ", " compatibility ", " congruity ", " harmoniousness ", " applicability ", " bearing ", " connection ", " justifiable ", " materiality ", " pertinence ", " Words such as relevance ", " relevance ", " validity acceptability ", " adequacy ", " adequateness ", " convenience ", " expedience ", " expediency ", " satisfactoriness ", " serviceableness ", " usefulness " (adjectives) can be expressed with Of these linguistic elements, the word "happy" is the most used in oral and written speech. At this point, we first look at the semantic features of the word "happy", including syntactic functions and morphological features and semantics, including lexical meaning, synonyms, antonyms, combinations and idioms, and interesting aspects of proverbs. we will go out..

The component "happy" is a typical adjective, which embodies the following semantic meanings of adjectives:

a) the pre-modified adjective with degree intensifiers such as "very", "so", "so very", "more than", "extremely", "too" comes at the beginning of the sentence or in front of the quality it is defining, and the component being defined is in the increasing degree indicates that it is, or is more or more than the usual amount, e.g. Other adverbs such as "very happy", "more than happy" (to express happiness that is not adequately expressed by the word "happy") and "reasonable", "completely", "perfectly" also express the component of happiness in English. comes before or after words to enhance their meaning. At the same time, each of the above-mentioned words has its scope and place of use. The use of such tools clearly shows the freedom of expression of the writer and the ability to use words. For example:

My early childhood was extremely happy .

Or we can take a closer look at the use of the happiness component in the works of famous English writers, for example, Jane Austen

In Emma:

Perfect happiness, even in memory, is not common.

Or, in an example from Amy Lowell's Sword blades and poppy seeds:

Happiness to me is wine.

Effervescent, superfine.

Full of tang and fiery pleasure.

Far too hot to leave me leisure

For a single thought beyond it.

We can see examples like this and through them we can see the scope of use of the component we are considering.

If we focus on the original origin and basis of the lexemes happy and unhappiness, it consists of one morpheme. We can find two inflectional word forms in them: happier (comparative-comparative) and happiest (superlative-superlative) by means of inflection; and by means of

this derivation five compounds "happiness" (n), "happily" (adv), "unhappy" (adj), "unhappiness" (n) and "unhappily" (adv) and 'happy event'(n), It can form compounds like 'happy hour' (n), 'happy medium' (n), 'happy-go-lucky' (adj), 'slap-happy' (adj), 'trigger-happy'.

There are several other cases where the adjective -y is formed.

"Happy event" consists of two roots, happy and event; "happy-hour" has two roots happy-happy and hour-hour; "happy medium" two roots happy and middle-medium; "happy-go-lucky" has three roots: happy, go, go ahead, lucky and suffix -y; 'slap-happy' has two roots directly, unobstructed-slap and happy-happy; and "trigger-happy" are also two roots trigger-trigger and happy-happy. The word "happy" can also be combined with nouns such as "money", "clothes" and "bomb" to form many compound nouns, such as "money-happy", "clothes-happy" and " can form "bomb-happy" compounds.

1. Feeling or showing pleasure and contentment-feeling or showing care and anxiety or sad-feeling or showing feelings of worry and unhappiness;
2. Causing or giving pleasure and contentment-causing or giving anxiety and care-causing or giving them;
3. Full of joy- full of joy, to show the acquired level of joy, or, Full of unhappiness- to express the acquired level of sadness;
4. Fortunate, lucky, or, Unfortunate, unsuccessful, failure, to express such feelings;
5. Suitable, appropriate - to express the appropriateness, or, Tactless, inappropriate, nonsuitable to express feelings of inappropriateness;
6. Willing- is used to express the feeling of desire, or Inwishes, indeseire- is used to express the lack of desire for an object.

Each of the above categories has a separate meaning and content, as well as separate forms, which we will consider in detail below:

Feeling or showing pleasure and contentment or Feeling or showing care and anxiety or sad
In this sense, "Happy" refers to the feeling of positive pleasure that a person feels. It's a neutral, generic, and all-encompassing term that we use to describe the feeling of enjoyment in all settings: life, marriage, work, social relationships, and so on. At this point, the word "unhappy" is considered the opposite of the word "happy" or the words used to express the feeling are considered neutral words in most cases and are used in everyday life and in fiction and on the pages of the press. we can meet plab. For example:

My mother was happy about my exam results .

We are very saddened by the loss of our dog, who is the best friend of our family and at the same time we are all hunters .

The words "happy" and "unhappy" are often used informally, formally and in various literature. In the sense of expressing feelings of pleasure and sadness, they are descriptive synonyms with "happy", "glad", "pleased", "delighted", "ecstatic", "elated" and "overjoyed", while "sad" - It is an antonym with the category "negative feeling or pleasure". "happy" and its derivative "unhappy" are the most commonly used words.

References:

1. Rusakova IB According to the data, the content of the concepts "happiness" - "unhappiness". Associative experiment 2006 - C 86-95. ASPushkin, 2005. - S. 90

2.Rusakova IB semantic network of the concepts "happiness" - "unhappiness" (on). annotated dictionaries) 2006 - Issue 3 (51) - C 132-136.

3.Rusakova Sh>. Mythological images of happiness and unhappiness in Russian are a picture of the world screaming (based on proverbs) May 15-18, 2006 - M • State. IRYA them AS Pushkin, 2006. - S. 230-237Alimpieva

